

On the creation of the universe, the planets and the atoms

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The creation of the universe is still a big mystery for humanity. The link with quantum theory is not obvious. Many discrepancies arise from such lacks in the existent theories. The BEN JBARA theory bands the links between the creation of the universe and the behavior of atoms and electrons. It provides explanations of why the theory of Einstein is wrong in predicting the Einstein rings behavior and why BEN JBARA theory seems to complete it with postulates that are more relevant. In this article, mine proposal THE BEN JBARA Theory, propose that the universe originated from a singular, cohesive energy that we call Nejib energy substrate. Rather than a vacuum, the field of the original energy acts like the fundamental block for all creation in the universe. In this article, we discuss the BEN JBARA Theory theorems and we verify its relevance through calculus of the energy matter ratio defined in classical theories.

The question of matter and its behavior is very important. Many applications can arise thanks to a more suitable theory "The BEN JBARA theory" that explains better why it is like that, again. The method here is an observation of some of the phenomenon discussed in literature such as universe behavior and planets formation and the relative confirmation of its reliability thanks to the discovery of an explanation of a constant value that states that the theory is relevant.

We start by explaining the theory postulates then we prove its relevance through a part of the calculus that may prove it, we explain the concept of Nejib rings as a replacement of Einstein theory, and we let the rest to other physics researchers to make the rest.

We start by explaining the phenomenon used in current theories. Based on literature experimental results we prove that the universe has a dark matter and a dark energy that we want to name Nejib Energy substrate in this theory.

When we think the universe creation, we postulate the following BEN JBARA theory.

In the beginning was the Nejib energy substrate, then a fluctuation with a set of axes and centers raised. From that fluctuation with many axis and centers, the matter of the universe with its current manifestation as a set of asters manifested. We can postulate that existent manifestation groups a set of matter elements having a big fluctuation axis or a center with a set of small matter with smaller axis or centers. For instance, there is the earth axis and some points within the earth as small fluctuations. The asters around like the sun can be a source of fluctuations such as the other parts of the galaxy. This can explain partially why galaxies can have elliptical or flat disks form rather than a spherical mass distribution. The second explanation of the galaxies forms is going to be provided later in this article.

We think that the universe matter is a globe, which is formed through a bigger fluctuation that has an axis or center forming the globe axis or centers that can be a rotational axis or centers for completely weird rotations. Our theory differs from current theories by stating that within the globe the light in one ring side travels through the dark matter or the eparpilled Nejib energy substrate not through a vacuum. But in the other ring side the light goes through vacuum and a sea of small quarks.

Hence, the theory postulates that there is always a volume or a globe were matter lives in different form around the fluctuation such as the globe of the universe for galaxies or the center of the earth like for atoms. Now let us explain in details the BEN JBARA theory.

Creation of the universe, the earth and the atoms as a single entity from the original energy substrate the Nejib energy:

When there is a fluctuation axis or center, the Nejib energy substrate reacts like water wave rings with a propagation. Let us illustrate that with what we discuss later in the next paragraph. After the permanent and punctual synchronous like periodic or aperiodic fluctuation strikes, the Nejib energy

substrates enlarge in volume and radius in a compression to a ring form. When reaching the final ring form the energy is likely to detach into smaller parts. Atoms only forms within what we call Nejib original energy rings. We note many rings due to the time permanence of the propagations of the strikes.

Outside of the original rings, the rings become Noah rings. Rings that detach due to the conservation of the original Nejib ring energy flow or volume and the enlargement of their radius to become light and small particles like dark matter building blocks quarks and other small particles and even atoms when small particles aggregate in different energy rings levels.

The Nejib original ring was confirmed in Astronomy internet article were a perfect like Einstein ring was used to find a satellite made almost of dark matter [1].

When the Noah rings detach or decompose into smaller parts the energy is transformed into light and very tiny dark matter called quarks. We postulate that photons are the energy glow that makes it one big entity. The Noah energy rings were confirmed in some observations. For instance, researchers estimates that the Ring mentioned in Einstein theory breaks into arcs. This argument suggests the presence of Noah BEN JBARA rings.

Many observations are mentioned in the nature article [2].

Now let's postulate about the formation of planets and atoms as single entities provided by agglomeration of small energy particles from various Noah energy rings when stretched and particles attracted together to bind in a given energy level to form a particular type of particles.

Let's explain the Three postulated theorems for the formation of atoms in the universe.

After the formation of the Noah BEN JBARA rings, the detached rings generates lights and quarks. But the quarks are returned through two forces to the Nejib BEN JBARA original rings and with the third phenomenon atoms like planets forms. The two forces as well the third phenomenon are explained as follows:

First, the Ayad Souabni attraction force, this force tends to return the wave to its original place just after the fluctuation strikes, like going from a concentrated ring to a less concentrated energy place in a vacuum.

Second, the repulsion force of Ayad Souabni, this force tends to eliminate the ring and push the quarks to another advanced level but the Ayad attraction force is more strong like what happens in the sea the morning and the evening...

Third, the force of bending between quarks at each level of a ring works like the join force of Boulettes of vegetarian meat formation motivated by the hand movements of the women is like my mother kitchen in old Tunisia and France. The light from a side with the quarks forms bigger particles like neutrino and protons than bands together. This image is to illustrate is from open source internet like kitchen normal examples.

The creation of planets is more particular were the heart of the earth is always submitted to the fluctuation and only the energy particles within the heart is moving in circles and rotating the entire planet around the axis of the fluctuation strikes or more the old fluctuation.

Now, let's develop the model that illustrate this to discover the ration between dark matter or the energy within Nejib original ring and the superior of the original ring of nejib or the start of Noah BEN JBARA rings.

Let's consider a fluctuation strike that perturbates a volume V of Nejib energy substrates. We consider the moved energy volume as a sphere with a radius R. The sphere is transformed into a ring with a radius r. To calculate the ratio we consider the next formulas:

$$\pi R^3 = \pi ((R+r)^3 - R^3)$$

$$\Omega = r/R = \sqrt[3]{2} - 1 = 0.25$$

Figure 1 Analogy of atoms and planets creation

To conclude the BEN JBARA theory addresses the universe, planet and atoms creation and propagation in the universe . This bends the ties between general relativity and current quantum mechanics theories .Thanks to this discovery the physical matter is better explained and well studied.BEN JEBARA theory will lead to better applications and more precise of physics theory.

References :

- [1] <https://www.astronomy.com/science/dwarf-dark-galaxy-hidden-in-alma-gravitational-lens-image>
- [2] Caldwell R, Kamionkowski M. Cosmology: Dark matter and dark energy. Nature. 2009 Apr 2;458(7238):587-9. doi: 10.1038/458587a. PMID: 19340073.